

Nano hydroxyapatite in bone regeneration: A literature review

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Abstract

Background: The tissue engineering technique to bone and periodontal tissue regeneration therapy that makes use of one or more of three key factors: signaling molecules, scaffold or supporting matrix, and cells. The graft works as a scaffold and a framework for forming a structure to aid tissue regeneration. One of the most generally used graft substances is hydroxyapatite (HAp). Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a calcium phosphate derivative that is commonly utilized in bone coatings and cements due to its exceptional biocompatibility. The topic of nano- hydroxyapatite (nHAp) in tissue regeneration therapy will be discussed in this publication.

Methods: The method used in writing this article review was a literature review sourced from Google Scholar, Science Direct, and PubMed (MEDLINE).

Result: The identification results from a search on Google Scholar, Science Direct, and PubMed (MEDLINE) in which the title contains one or more keywords being searched for, from the article, 55 articles are obtained that have appropriate titles and 14 data are obtained from the results of the review.

Discussion: Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a bioceramic material formed from strong chemical bonds and is included in the bone components of living organisms (in vivo). Conclusion: Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a bioceramic substance made up of a strong chemical link that is a derivative of calcium phosphate. It is commonly used in coatings or cements on bone because of its excellent biocompatibility.

Keywords: Bone Graft; Hydroxyapatite; Nano Hydroxyapatite; Medicine

1. Introduction

Bone graft is a support material that has been extensively studied and advanced rapidly to acquire periodontal tissue regeneration¹. Graft is a synthetic or natural material that acts as a filler that also functions as a scaffold and is able to begin the method of bone formation². In the primary phase of regeneration, bone grafts aid in the attachment and proliferation of cells in the defect area, as well as the stability of blood clots to prevent tissue injury^{2,3,4}. Autograft, allograft, xenograft, and alloplast are the several varieties of graft materials, each having its private set of advantages and disadvantages. As a result, researchers are continually looking for alternative replacements that have more predictable regeneration outcomes and less side effects^{5,6}

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2. Methods

The method used in writing this article review was a literature review sourced from Google Scholar, Science Direct, and PubMed (MEDLINE). The strategy used in data collection was in the form of writing keywords that were used to find articles to be reviewed with a publication period between 2011-2021. The keywords used were bone graft, hydroxyapatite, nano hydroxyapatite, medicine.

Table 1 Tracking scientific articles

No.	Keywords	Year	Database	Number of Articles
1.	Bone Graft	2011-2021	Google Scholar	7700
			Science Direct	941
			PubMed	624
2.	Hydroxyapatite		Google Scholar	3800
			Science Direct	974
			PubMed	998
3.	Nano Hydroxyapatite		Google Scholar	2.103
			Science Direct	571
			PubMed	420
4.	Medicine		Google Scholar	2400
			Science Direct	607
			PubMed	959

3. Results

The identification results from a search on Google Scholar, Science Direct, and PubMed (MEDLINE) in which the title contains one or more keywords being searched for, from the article, 55 articles are obtained that have appropriate titles and 14 data are obtained from the results of the review. There are 3 Indonesian journal articles and 66 international journal articles. The next step is the process of screening the search results data, the results of data types that have similarities in the research theme are obtained. The eligibility stage is carried out to determine which articles enter the inclusion and exclusion criteria based on the suitability of the title and content of the article. Then the include stage is a search with inclusion criteria, namely articles with a time limit of the last eleven years that have been set by the author in the form of studies related to the topic: Nano Hydroxyapatite in Bone Regeneration.

4. Discussion

4.1. Hydroxyapatite

Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a bioceramic material formed from strong chemical bonds and is included in the bone components of living organisms (in vivo)⁷. Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a derivative of calcium phosphate which is most widely used in coatings or cements on bone because it has excellent biocompatible properties⁸. The Ca/P ratio of calcium phosphate hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) is 1.67^{9,10}. Biomaterials made from HAp consist of HAp cement, HAp nonporous, HAp porous, nano HAp, and bioceramics (which has a greater compact structure when compared to different formations)⁸.

4.2. Hydroxyapatite Sources

In addition to human bones and teeth (allograft), the source of this hydroxyapatite is obtained from animal bones or other sources (xenograft) in inorganic and organic forms. Inorganic sources such as rocks containing phosphate. While organic sources, for example, come from chicken egg shells, clam shells, fish bones and cow bones^{11,12,13}. HAp may be made with the synthetic substances used within the sol-gel technique. However, based on the results of research that

has been carried out, hydroxyapatite made from natural materials is better in terms of crystal size, biocompatible and non-toxic to cells, besides that it is also more economical in terms of raw materials¹⁴.

4.3. Advantages of Hydroxyapatite

Biocompatible, bioactive, and bioresorbable are only a several of the properties of hydroxyapatite (HAp). Biocompatibility is the property where the material does not cause a rejection reaction from the human immune system. The bioactive properties will cause the material to be slightly soluble but help form a biological surface layer before directly interacting with tissue and forming chemical bonds with bone¹⁵. The material's bioresorbable characteristics aid in the formation and reabsorption of bone tissue, allowing it to be used as a scaffold or filler to fill and repair the tissue^{15,16,17,18,19}.

The chemical similarity of the mineral phase to bone is HAp's most unique feature, resulting in excellent osteoconductive ability and biocompatibility^{20,21,22,23}. Examples of the use of HAp composite materials and in the field of periodontics are used as bone graft materials²⁴. Biocompatibility, cell adhesion, and functional support are all advantages of hydroxyapatite made from natural materials^{25,26,27,28}.

HAp has inelastic and brittle properties which can limit its synthesis ability in the desired shape or structure, so that it can affect the capacity of bone regeneration. Several methods can be used to solve HAp's weaknesses: to improve osteoconduction, the size and porosity of HAp can be modified; to overcome brittleness and improve osteoconduction even greater, it's far combined with other polymers; combined with growth factors, cells and/or molecules for better osteoinductivity (Bal et al, 2019)^{28,29}.

4.4. Nano Hydroxyapatite

Nanoparticle materials are increasingly developing in medicine. One of the materials that is being developed into nanoparticles is hydroxyapatite.

Bioactivity, osteoconductivity, osteoinductivity, degradation rate, porosity, and material surface properties are all elements to consider in bone regeneration³¹. Cell-to-cell communication, cell mobility, cellular adhesion, proliferation, differentiation, and biodegradation are all affected by porosity size, at the same time as bioactivity and cell adhesion are affected by material surface characteristics^{28,32,33,34,35,36}. Increased porosity will improve the amount of body fluids that come into contact with each surface area, as well as the material's bioactivity^{28,32,37}.

Figure 1 Bone structure at all scales, from macro to micro³⁰

Porosity and pore length are crucial for touch with body fluids and tissue vascularization^{28,32,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45}. Improved porosity allows greater fluids to contact the composite, permitting growth factors like VEGF to penetrate the clot and promote vascularization and angiogenesis^{28,44,45,46,47}. Advanced new bone growth, vascularity, protein and cell adhesion are all advantages of improved porosity. It additionally improves the biodegradability of the material to the specified stage. However, if the implant fails, the biocomposite's mechanical strength may be compromised, particularly in the load-bearing area^{28,39,40}. Although the benefits increase due to the porosity of the material, care must be taken about the risk of loss of mechanical strength, and a balance must be found²⁸.

4.5. Advantages of Nano Hydroxyapatite

Bayani et al. (2017) published a take a look at in the journal on the properties of nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite as a bone graft material within the treatment of periodontal problems. In periodontal tissue regeneration, nano hydroxyapatite is probably a less high-priced possibility to autogenous bone grafts⁴⁸. It is critical in tissue engineering to offer bioactive materials with the necessary mechanical characteristics and, in most cases, degradation rates that are identical to the tissue's original structure²⁸.

HAp nanoparticles are more similar to natural hydroxyapatite found in bone than micro- sized hydroxyapatite. Here are some advantages of nano HAp⁴⁹:

- Have closer contact with the surrounding network
- Has properties that are more quickly absorbed and a high number of molecules on the surface
- The attachment of osteoblasts and osteoclasts is more formed on the nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite than conventional hydroxyapatite
- Have good bioaffinity
- This could help in the integration of bone, the expression of collagen I, and the differentiation of osteoblasts.

Nanomaterials have benefits in material stiffness, effective surface place, and location- volume ratio because of smaller particle length⁵⁰. At the nanometric scale, natural bone is formed by a highly organized extracellular matrix (ECM), and the use of nano-scaffold can benefit tissue engineering methods^{51,52,53}. Nanomaterials have the ability to solve difficulties with current bone regeneration scaffold, along with mechanical vulnerable factors, instability of released growth elements and the presence of impaired cell differentiation^{50,51,54,56,57,58,59}.

4.6. The Role of Nano Hydroxyapatite in Tissue Regeneration

Nanoparticles have a greater surface area to volume ratio and a higher strength gradient on the surface than microparticles. Three-dimensional modelling and simulation can be used to optimize the shape of the nanoparticles and the character of the scaffold to shape the scale and shape of the repaired bone defect⁶⁰.

Nutrition absorption and protein adsorption can improve the wettability of large-surface- area nanoparticles. When designing composite materials, nHAp is used as a strong filler material, to improve the mechanical stability of composite materials, increase cell proliferation, adhesion, and differentiation, consisting of stem cells, with the aid of increasing interactions among cells. Through selective protein adsorption, nHAp can also help cell surface contacts^{60,61}.

For bone regeneration and composite strength, porosity and stoichiometry are important. As the porosity of the composite improves, so does the ability to build bones, as does the integration of body fluids with the composite²⁸.

While nHAp has a tiny particle size and a wide surface area, it can resorb quickly and be replaced by essential bone more quickly. According to the preceding observation, whole nHAp resorption takes 12 weeks. Maintaining the post-extraction socket and minimizing the quantity of graft material around the dental implant is a good idea^{48,62}. When Canullo et al. (2015) studied post- extraction sockets grafted with nHAp (including Mg), they discovered that the hard tissue around the graft had completely healed. Additionally, at the time of the study, the graft material had experienced significant resorption^{48,63}.

Webster et al. (2000) reported increased osteoblast and protein adhesion observed in the nanophase of alumina, titanium, and HAp compared to conventional forms due to reduced material size as well as increased surface area. As a result, the number of cells attaching to the surface of the material has improved^{28,64,65,66}. According to Tavakol et al. (2013) the material's surface morphology and wettability were essential elements in bone regeneration^{48,63}.

4.7. Mechanism of Nano Hydroxyapatite Signaling

To understand the mechanism involved in nHAp signaling, the research conducted by Ha et al. (2015) was carried out in several stages so that the mechanism of nHAp was received by the FGF receptor (FGFR) and Phosphate Transporter (PiT), then received by the FRS 2 α receptor, then continued to activate the center of the ERK to express the gene. The ERK 1/2 pathway is required for nHAp activation in OPN expression. Thus, OPN expression induced by nHAp involves the major components FGFR and PiT and is mediated by the MEK-ERK 1/2 pathway^{28,67}. Expression genes that are activated by ERK 1/2 will produce 2 groups, namely Up-regulation and Down-regulation. Up regulation (Amyloid A3

and Lipocalin) and down regulation (VDR, IGF-1, IGF-2, and Osterix). Osterix will activate pre-osteoblasts to become osteoblasts^{28,67}.

Figure 2 Signaling centers formed by nHAp that induce gene expression changes are shown in this image²⁸

4.8. Nano Hydroxyapatite on Growth Factor Release

Lock and Liu (2011) suggested that n-HA present in scaffold nanocomposites might stimulate undifferentiated mesenchymal cell attachment and differentiation in a manner similar to shortening BMP-7 from bone. Zhou et al. (2008) compared the n-HA particle films to the hydroxyapatite particle films, found a lot of protein on the n-HA films^{48,68}. Furthermore, Jain et al. (2012) showed that the degradation of calcium sulphate particles, which lowers local pH, would possibly lead to wall defect demineralization and the release of growth elements such BMP-2,

BMP-7, TGF- β , and PDGF-BB^{48,69}. The findings of a study by Pezzatini et al. (2007) showed that n-HA will increase endothelial cell proliferation through upregulating FGF-248,62. The outcomes of this study display that n-HA can enhance the response of cells to VEGF^{48,69}

5. Conclusion

Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a bioceramic substance made up of a strong chemical link that is a derivative of calcium phosphate. It is commonly used in coatings or cements on bone because of its excellent biocompatibility. Bioactive materials that can imitate the tissue's original structure are important in tissue engineering. Nano HAp proved to be better than micro particles because it has a rougher surface and a larger cross-sectional area. In addition, research has shown that nano- hydroxyapatite exhibits several advantages, including minimal toxicity and when applied with biological particles such as fibroblasts, osteoblasts and osteoclasts additionally cause a positive response inside the regeneration of periodontal tissue.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Newman MG, Carranza FA, Takei HH, Klokkevold PR. *Newman and Carranza's Clinical Periodontology*. 11th ed. Amsterdam: Elsevier Health Science; 2011.
- [2] Rios HF, Bashutski JD, McAllister BS, Murakami S, Cobb CM, Patricia Chun YH, et al. Emerging Regenerative Approaches for Periodontal Reconstruction: Practical Applications From the AAP Regeneration Workshop. *Clin Adv Periodontics* [Internet]. 2015 Feb;5(1):40–6. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1902/cap.2015.140052>
- [3] Prahasanti C, Subrata LH, Saskianti T, Suardita K, Ernawati DS. Combined Hydroxyapatite Scaffold and Stem Cell from Human Exfoliated Deciduous Teeth Modulating Alveolar Bone Regeneration via Regulating Receptor Activator of Nuclear Factor-Kb and Osteoprotegerin System. *Iran J Med Sci*. 2019 Sep;44(5):415–21.
- [4] Sudarmono S, Widyaputra S, Sitam S, Suherna I, Fitri AD, Rachman A. Comparison of Bone regeneration in hADMSC Versus hUCBMSC with hBMMSC as a Reference: A Literature Review of Potential Bone Regeneration. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2021 Apr 29;14(4):1993–8. Available from: <https://rjptonline.org/AbstractView.aspx?PID=2021-14-4-29>
- [5] Asa'ad F, Pagni G, Pilipchuk SP, Gianni AB, Giannobile W V., Rasperini G. 3D-Printed Scaffolds and Biomaterials: Review of Alveolar Bone Augmentation and Periodontal Regeneration Applications. *Int J Dent* [Internet]. 2016;2016:1–15. Available from: <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/ijd/2016/1239842/>
- [6] Oryan A, Alidadi S, Moshiri A, Maffulli N. Bone regenerative medicine: classic options, novel strategies, and future directions. *J Orthop Surg Res*. 2014 Mar;9(1):18.
- [7] Jayaswal GP, Dange SP, Khalikar AN. Bioceramic in dental implants: A review. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc* [Internet]. 2010 Mar 5;10(1):8–12. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13191-010-0002-4>
- [8] Al-Sanabani JS, Madfa AA, Al-Sanabani FA. Application of calcium phosphate materials in dentistry. *Int J Biomater*. 2013;2013:876132.
- [9] Bano N, Jikan SS, Basri H, Adzila S, Nuhu AH. Natural Hydroxyapatite Extracted From Bovine Bone. *J Sci Technol*. 2017;9(2):22–8.
- [10] Figueiredo M, Fernando A, Martins G, Freitas J, Judas F, Figueiredo H. Effect of the calcination temperature on the composition and microstructure of hydroxyapatite derived from human and animal bone. *Ceram Int* [Internet]. 2010;36(8):2383–93. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272884210002683>
- [11] Fadhilah N, Irhamni I, Jalil Z. Synthesis of Natural Hydroxyapatite From Aceh's Bovine Bone. *J Aceh Phys Soc*. 2016;5(2):19–21.
- [12] Akram M, Ahmed R, Shakir I, Ibrahim WAW, Hussain R. Extracting hydroxyapatite and its precursors from natural resources. *J Mater Sci* [Internet]. 2014;49(4):1461–75. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-013-7864-x>
- [13] Girija C, Sivakumar MN. Amalgamation and Characterization of Hydroxyapatite Powders from Eggshell for Functional Biomedical Application. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2018;11(10):4242. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=11&issue=10&article=007>
- [14] Rahavi SS, Ghaderi O, Monshi A, Fathi MH. A comparative study on physicochemical properties of hydroxyapatite powders derived from natural and synthetic sources. *Russ J Non-Ferrous Met* [Internet]. 2017 May 16;58(3):276–86. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.3103/S1067821217030178>
- [15] Suryadi. *Sintesis dan Karakterisasi Biomaterial Hidroksiapatit dengan Proses Pengendapan Kimia Basah*. Universitas Indonesia; 2011.
- [16] Jose H, Krishnakumar K, Dineshkumar B. Herbal extracts based scaffolds for wound healing therapy. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2021;14(3):1805–10. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=14&issue=3&article=109>
- [17] Aswin SK, Jothishwar S, Nayagam PVC, Priya G. Scaffolds for Biomolecule Delivery and Controlled Release-A Review. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2018;11(10):4719. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=11&issue=10&article=091>

- [18] Kamadjaja MJK, Salim S, Subiakto BDS. Application of Hydroxyapatite scaffold from *Portunus pelagicus* on OPG and RANKL expression after tooth extraction of *Cavia cobaya*. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2021 Sep 14;4647–51. Available from: <https://rjptonline.org/AbstractView.aspx?PID=2021-14-9-21>
- [19] Nugraha AP, Rezkita F, Puspitaningrum MS, Luthfimaedah MS, Narmada IB, Prahasanti C, et al. Gingival Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Chitosan Scaffold to Accelerate Alveolar Bone Remodelling in Periodontitis: A Narrative Review. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2020;13(5):2502. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=13&issue=5&article=076>
- [20] Darwis D, Warastuti Y. Sintesis dan Karakterisasi Komposit Hidroksiapatit (HA) Sebagai Graft Tulang Sintetik. *A Sci J Appl Isot Radiat*. 2008;4(2):143–53.
- [21] Phillips GO. Allograft in Orthopaedic. In: *Advanced in Tissue Banking*. 1st ed. Singapore: World Scientific; 1997.
- [22] Nagai H, Nishimura Y. Hydroxyapatite, ceramic material and process for preparing thereof. United State; 4,448,758, 1984.
- [23] Yusong P, Dangsheng X, Xiaolin C. Mechanical properties of nanohydroxyapatite reinforced poly(vinyl alcohol) gel composites as biomaterial. *J Mater Sci* [Internet]. 2007;42(13):5129–34. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-006-1264-4>
- [24] Remya NS, Syama S, Gayathri V, Varma HK, Mohanan PV. An in vitro study on the interaction of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles and bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells for assessing the toxicological behaviour. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces* [Internet]. 2014 May;117:389–97. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0927776514000605>
- [25] Mondal S, Pal U. 3D hydroxyapatite scaffold for bone regeneration and local drug delivery applications. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol* [Internet]. 2019 Oct;53:101131. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1773224719305064>
- [26] Mondal S, Mondal A, Mandal N, Mondal B, Mukhopadhyay SS, Dey A, et al. Physico- chemical characterization and biological response of *Labeo rohita*-derived hydroxyapatite scaffold. *Bioprocess Biosyst Eng* [Internet]. 2014 Jul 28;37(7):1233–40. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00449-013-1095-z>
- [27] Manivasagan P, Bharathiraja S, Santha Moorthy M, Mondal S, Seo H, Dae Lee K, et al. Marine natural pigments as potential sources for therapeutic applications. *Crit Rev Biotechnol* [Internet]. 2018 Jul 4;38(5):745–61. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/07388551.2017.1398713>
- [28] Bal Z, Kaito T, Korkusuz F, Yoshikawa H. Bone regeneration with hydroxyapatite-based biomaterials. *Emergent Mater* [Internet]. 2020 Aug 19;3(4):521–44. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s42247-019-00063-3>
- [29] Kankilic B, Dede EC, Korkusuz P, Timuçin M, Korkusuz F. Apatites for Orthopedic Applications. In: *Clinical Applications of Biomaterials* [Internet]. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2017. p. 65–90. Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-56059-5_3
- [30] Haider A, Haider S, Han SS, Kang IK. Recent advances in the synthesis, functionalization and biomedical applications of hydroxyapatite: a review. *RSC Adv* [Internet]. 2017;7(13):7442–58. Available from: <http://xlink.rsc.org/?DOI=C6RA26124H>
- [31] Hannink G, Arts JJC. Bioresorbability, porosity and mechanical strength of bone substitutes: What is optimal for bone regeneration? *Injury* [Internet]. 2011 Sep;42:S22–5. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0020138311002452>
- [32] Jeong J, Kim JH, Shim JH, Hwang NS, Heo CY. Bioactive calcium phosphate materials and applications in bone regeneration. *Biomater Res* [Internet]. 2019 Dec 14;23(1):4. Available from: <https://biomaterialsres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40824-018-0149-3>
- [33] Dorozhkin S V. Nanodimensional and Nanocrystalline Calcium Orthophosphates. *Am J Biomed Eng* [Internet]. 2012 Aug 31;2(3):48–97. Available from: 10.5923/j.ajbe.20120203.01
- [34] Rouahi M, Champion E, Gallet O, Jada A, Anselme K. Physico-chemical characteristics and protein adsorption potential of hydroxyapatite particles: Influence on in vitro biocompatibility of ceramics after sintering. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces* [Internet]. 2006 Jan;47(1):10–9. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0927776505003322>

- [35] Wada T, Nakashima T, Hiroshi N, Penninger JM. RANKL–RANK signaling in osteoclastogenesis and bone disease. *Trends Mol Med* [Internet]. 2006 Jan;12(1):17–25. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1471491405002674>
- [36] Matsiko A, Gleeson JP, O'Brien FJ. Scaffold mean pore size influences mesenchymal stem cell chondrogenic differentiation and matrix deposition. *Tissue Eng Part A*. 2015 Feb;21(3–4):486–97.
- [37] Korkusuz F, Timuçin M, Korkusuz P. Nanocrystalline Apatite-Based Biomaterials and Stem Cells in Orthopaedics BT - *Advances in Calcium Phosphate Biomaterials*. In: Ben-Nissan B, editor. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2014. p. 373–90. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-53980-0_12
- [38] Zhu XD, Zhang HJ, Fan HS, Li W, Zhang XD. Effect of phase composition and microstructure of calcium phosphate ceramic particles on protein adsorption. *Acta Biomater* [Internet]. 2010;6(4):1536–41. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S174270610900467X>
- [39] Yoshikawa H, Tamai N, Murase T, Myoui A. Interconnected porous hydroxyapatite ceramics for bone tissue engineering. *J R Soc Interface*. 2009 Jun;6 Suppl 3(Suppl 3):S341-8.
- [40] Dorozhkin S V, Epple M. Biological and medical significance of calcium phosphates. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl*. 2002 Sep;41(17):3130–46.
- [41] Bouler JM, Pilet P, Gauthier O, Verron E. Biphasic calcium phosphate ceramics for bone reconstruction: A review of biological response. *Acta Biomater*. 2017 Apr;53:1–12.
- [42] Ramay HRR, Zhang M. Biphasic calcium phosphate nanocomposite porous scaffolds for load-bearing bone tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* [Internet]. 2004;25(21):5171–80. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142961203011724>
- [43] Canillas M, Pena P, de Aza AH, Rodríguez MA. Calcium phosphates for biomedical applications. *Boletín la Soc Española Cerámica y Vidr* [Internet]. 2017;56(3):91–112. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0366317517300444>
- [44] Li J, Zhi W, Xu T, Shi F, Duan K, Wang J, et al. Ectopic osteogenesis and angiogenesis regulated by porous architecture of hydroxyapatite scaffolds with similar interconnecting structure in vivo. *Regen Biomater*. 2016 Oct;3(5):285–97.
- [45] Xia L, Lin K, Jiang X, Xu Y, Zhang M, Chang J, et al. Enhanced osteogenesis through nano-structured surface design of macroporous hydroxyapatite bioceramic scaffolds via activation of ERK and p38 MAPK signaling pathways. *J Mater Chem B* [Internet]. 2013;1(40):5403. Available from: <http://xlink.rsc.org/?DOI=c3tb20945h>
- [46] Sun X, Kang Y, Bao J, Zhang Y, Yang Y, Zhou X. Modeling vascularized bone regeneration within a porous biodegradable CaP scaffold loaded with growth factors. *Biomaterials*. 2013 Jul;34(21):4971–81.
- [47] Wang W, Yeung KWK. Bone grafts and biomaterials substitutes for bone defect repair: A review. *Bioact Mater*. 2017 Dec;2(4):224–47.
- [48] Bayani M, Torabi S, Shahnaz A, Pournali M. Main properties of nanocrystalline hydroxyapatite as a bone graft material in treatment of periodontal defects. A review of literature. *Biotechnol Equip* [Internet]. 2017 Mar 4;31(2):215–20. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13102818.2017.1281760>
- [49] Pascawinata A, Prihartiningsih P, Dwirahardjo B. Perbandingan Proses Penyembuhan Tulang pada Implantasi Hidroksiapatit Nanokristalin dengan Hidroksiapatit Mikrokristalin (Kajian Pada Tulang Tibia Kelinci). *B-Dent, J Kedokt Gigi Univ Baiturrahmah* [Internet]. 2014 Nov 10;1(1):1–10. Available from: <https://jurnal.unbrah.ac.id/index.php/bdent/article/view/45>
- [50] Walmsley GG, McArdle A, Tevlin R, Momeni A, Atashroo D, Hu MS, et al. Nanotechnology in bone tissue engineering. *Nanomedicine*. 2015 Jul;11(5):1253–63.
- [51] Funda G, Taschieri S, Bruno GA, Grecchi E, Paolo S, Girolamo D, et al. Nanotechnology Scaffolds for Alveolar Bone Regeneration. *Mater (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2020 Jan;13(1).
- [52] Carbone EJ, Jiang T, Nelson C, Henry N, Lo KWH. Small molecule delivery through nanofibrous scaffolds for musculoskeletal regenerative engineering. *Nanomedicine*. 2014 Nov;10(8):1691–9.
- [53] Deng M, James R, Laurencin CT, Kumbar SG. Nanostructured polymeric scaffolds for orthopaedic regenerative engineering. *IEEE Trans Nanobioscience*. 2012 Mar;11(1):3–14.

- [54] D'Amora U, Russo T, Gloria A, Riviaccio V, D'Antò V, Negri G, et al. 3D additive- manufactured nanocomposite magnetic scaffolds: Effect of the application mode of a time- dependent magnetic field on hMSCs behavior. *Bioact Mater.* 2017 Sep;2(3):138–45.
- [55] M.P. R, R.S. A, G.R. K. Nanofibers – A Newer Technology. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2021 Apr 29;2321–7. Available from: <https://rjptonline.org/AbstractView.aspx?PID=2021-14-4-86>
- [56] Vikran, Patel N, Parmar J, Gupta A, Choudhary R. Aquasome: A Self Assembling Nanoparticulate Drug Carrier System. *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2012;5(10):1320–3.
- [57] Singh S, Pal A, Mohanty S. Nano Structure of Hydroxyapatite and its modern approach in Pharmaceutical Science. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2019;12(3):1463. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=12&issue=3&article=082>
- [58] Patel SR, Shah DP. A Review on Nanocrystals Drug Delivery System. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2015;8(5):647. Available from: <http://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:rjpt&volume=8&issue=5&article=020>
- [59] Mohamed EA, Elbarbary AM, Abd alaty NMM, Ibrahim NK, Said MM, Salem AM. The Beneficial Effect of Nanostructured Oligochitosan against Gamma Irradiation and/or Carbon Tetrachloride-Induced Hepatic Injury in Rats. *Res J Pharm Technol* [Internet]. 2021 Apr 29;2243–57. Available from: <https://rjptonline.org/AbstractView.aspx?PID=2021-14-4-74>
- [60] Lowe B, Hardy JG, Walsh LJ. Optimizing Nanohydroxyapatite Nanocomposites for Bone Tissue Engineering. *ACS Omega* [Internet]. 2020 Jan 14;5(1):1–9. Available from: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsomega.9b02917>
- [61] Gong T, Xie J, Liao J, Zhang T, Lin S, Lin Y. Nanomaterials and bone regeneration. *Bone Res* [Internet]. 2015 Dec 10;3(1):15029. Available from: <http://www.nature.com/articles/boneres201529>
- [62] Pezzatini S, Morbidelli L, Solito R, Paccagnini E, Boanini E, Bigi A, et al. Nanostructured HA crystals up-regulate FGF-2 expression and activity in microvascular endothelium promoting angiogenesis. *Bone.* 2007 Oct;41(4):523–34.
- [63] Canullo L, Wiel Marin G, Tallarico M, Canciani E, Musto F, Dellavia C. Histological and Histomorphometrical Evaluation of Postextractive Sites Grafted with Mg-Enriched Nano-Hydroxyapatite: A Randomized Controlled Trial Comparing 4 Versus 12 Months of Healing. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.* 2016 Oct;18(5):973–83.
- [64] Webster TJ, Siegel RW, Bizios R. Osteoblast adhesion on nanophase ceramics. *Biomaterials.* 1999 Jul;20(13):1221–7.
- [65] Webster TJ, Ergun C, Doremus RH, Siegel RW, Bizios R. Enhanced functions of osteoblasts on nanophase ceramics. *Biomaterials.* 2000 Sep;21(17):1803–10.
- [66] Webster TJ, Ergun C, Doremus RH, Siegel RW, Bizios R. Specific proteins mediate enhanced osteoblast adhesion on nanophase ceramics. *J Biomed Mater Res.* 2000 Sep;51(3):475–83.
- [67] Ha SW, Jang HL, Nam KT, Beck GRJ. Nano-hydroxyapatite modulates osteoblast lineage commitment by stimulation of DNA methylation and regulation of gene expression. *Biomaterials.* 2015 Oct;65:32–42.
- [68] Lock J, Liu H. Nanomaterials enhance osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells similar to a short peptide of BMP-7. *Int J Nanomedicine.* 2011;6:2769–77.
- [69] Jain A, Chaturvedi R, Pahuja B. Comparative Evaluation of the Efficacy of Calcium Sulfate Bone Grafts in Crystalline and Nano-Crystalline Forms in Fresh Extraction Socket Sites: A Radiographic and Histological Pilot Study. *Int J Oral Implantol Clin Res* [Internet]. 2012 Apr;3(1):58–61. Available from: <https://www.ijoicr.com/doi/10.5005/JP-Journals-10012-1067>